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Added in Translation: Keywords for the Study of Javanese Islamic Texts

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Abstract

The idea of keywords was introduced in Raymond Williams' seminal *Keywords. A Vocabulary of Culture and Society* (1976), and has since had a profound influence on research in multiple fields.

This article explores what the idea of keywords might contribute to the study of interlinear translations from Arabic into Javanese. The interlinear translation, which presents an Arabic text with a word-for-word Javanese translation appearing between its lines, is a space where languages, beliefs, and entire histories encounter one another on the page. Taking as my example the 1864 interlinear *Babad Maulud* (a Javanese translation of the Arabic *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām*, recited on the Prophet Muhammad's birthday), I suggest that despite the Javanese translator's overall literal translation strategy which attempted to duplicate the original, he or she decided to add "Javanese keywords" at particular points in the translation, with such exceptions revealing contemporary Javanese understandings of social etiquette, identity and genealogy.

Keywords

keywords – Raymond Williams – interlinear translation – Islamic texts – Javanese literature – *maulid*

Introduction

This study discusses a nineteenth-century interlinear translation from Arabic to Javanese in the context of Javanese-Islamic textual production. Interlinear translations that include an original text with a typically word-for-word translation of that text written between the lines expand our understanding of translation paradigms and have the potential to enrich the field of translation studies, especially when the texts examined come from regions that have received relatively little attention. In this case, however, my main focus is not on interlinear translation per se—a rich topic that encompasses questions of grammar, visual culture and educational settings, among others—but on how the theoretical lens of keywords, first popularized by the British scholar of culture Raymond Williams, may offer a path to new insights on interlinear translations from Java as sites of revealing encounters, philological and otherwise.

I begin with a brief introduction to the world of Javanese-Islamic translation, then move on to the idea of keywords, followed by a textual example, analysis and conclusions.

Javanese-Islamic Translation Paradigms

A few words on Islamic translations traditions in the Indonesian-Malay world, in which Java is embedded, are in order.¹ I have suggested elsewhere that there were three main translation paradigms central to the spread of Islam in the region: those at the level of the story, sentence, and single word.² I briefly reiterate them here. The first paradigm, that of “holistic translation,” includes above all stories, typically works in Arabic or Persian that were written anew. These present a high level of creativity and flexibility that corresponds with authors’ tastes and agendas. Such translations differ in their level of correspondence

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- 1 The “Indonesian-Malay world” refers to the area roughly encompassing present day Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Brunei, southern Thailand and the southern Philippines, and diasporas in South Africa and Sri Lanka. Malay was for several centuries a lingua franca of trade, travel, diplomacy and Islamization; Javanese is the language of Indonesia’s largest ethnic group and possesses its longest continuous literary tradition.
 - 2 This section draws on Ronit Ricci, “Story, Sentence, Single Word: Translation Paradigms in Javanese and Malay Islamic Literature,” in *A Companion to Translation Studies*, ed. Sandra Bermann and Catherine Porter (Chichester: Wiley Blackwell, 2014), 543–56. The findings relate to both Javanese and Malay writings which share these translation paradigms but since the present study focuses on Javanese I refer to translation into that language only.

with the source text and show great variation in the strategies employed to make the foreign sound more familiar. In some cases such texts can be linked with a particular source but in others they cannot and for their audiences, who had access only to the translation, the translated text was *the* story.

The second paradigm transpired at the sentence level, when a sentence in Arabic was translated into Javanese. Such sentences could be embedded in a text that was largely written in Javanese or one in which alternating between two languages—Arabic and Javanese—could go on for many pages. Because in most such texts Javanese was written in the Arabic script (*pegon* or *gundhul*) the languages of original and translation seem to flow into and from one another on the page.³

The Javanese word *tegesi* or *tegesipun* ('this means, 'this signifies') was often the bridge at the end of the Arabic sentence and the beginning of its translation. Its presence allowed for Arabic content and sound to be included in the Javanese text while also remaining differentiated within it. For audiences of listeners rather than for readers of the text this word played an important aural role by signaling that an Arabic quote had concluded and they could now expect a translation and often an interpretation. The third translation paradigm was interlinear. Interlinear translation provided the reader with a word-for-word rendering of an Arabic text, with Javanese "equivalents" appearing between the Arabic lines on the page. Originating in the practice of interlinear translation of the Qur'ān in the early translations from Arabic to Persian and possessing a long history in the Muslim world before its adoption by translators in Southeast Asia, it became widely popular in the region since at least the sixteenth century.⁴

When translating entire works in an imaginative way or when conveying the general or even detailed sense of a sentence (the first and second translation paradigms), some thorny translation issues could be circumvented. However, in an interlinear translation the question of how to best represent elements such as number, gender and tense as they are expressed in Arabic had to be creatively addressed. More broadly, a major fault line runs between the holistic

3 Both names refer to Javanese written in a modified form of the Arabic script: *pegon* is vocalized while *gundhul* (literally "hairless, bald") is not.

4 The Dutch scholar Van Ronkel's work, although over a century old, remains the most extensive study to date of such translations from Arabic to Malay in the Indonesian-Malay region. One of his key findings was pointing to a standardization in the way Malay scholars and scribes translated Arabic words, idioms and grammatical particles into Malay. Philippus van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalamat Arab terhadap Tatakalamat Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram (Jakarta: Bharatara, 1977 [1899]). My own preliminary research suggests a similar pattern in Javanese interlinear translation.

translations on the one hand and the sentence and word-level paradigms on the other, with the latter always including the Arabic text on the page, available for reference, study, and comparison.

Keywords

The investigation of “keywords” as indicators for central concepts and topics within a socio-cultural community has a long history in linguistics and related fields, although not necessarily using “keyword” as a term. Already in the 1930s the British linguist J.R. Firth promoted the study of the “distribution of sociologically important words, what one might call focal or pivotal words in all their derivatives and compounds in sociologically significant contexts.”⁵

Within the history of understanding the use of words in socio-cultural contexts, or thinking in terms of keywords, Raymond Williams’ book *Keywords: A Vocabulary of Culture and Society* (1976) had a seminal influence. Looking at his own UK society after returning from military service during World War II and feeling that profound changes were apace, Williams began exploring individual words as a way to understand the shifting world around him through what he called a “historical semantics:” exploring how, reflecting historical change, specific words change their meaning over time, yet important words often retain some imprint of their former sense and are, to quote Craig Jeffrey, writing of keywords in India, “like a palimpsest.”⁶ The words selected by Williams (which were originally to be included as an appendix in his 1956 *Culture and Society* but became far too numerous) had to satisfy one of two conditions in order to be included in his book: a word had to be a “strong, important and persuasive word”⁷ that was circulating in ordinary society, or it had to be a word that had emerged out of a specialized context but had come to describe wider areas of thought and experience. Williams also defined his goal as an “inquiry into a vocabulary,” one in which individual words but also the relationships among them, the need to consider them in interrelated clusters (e.g., “culture” with “art” and “class,” or with “industry” and “democracy”) was central. Particular words, their pasts, presents, and complex entanglements with other words

5 J.R. Firth, “The Technique of Semantics,” *Transactions of the Philological Society* 34, no. 1 (1935): 40.

6 Craig Jeffrey and John Harriss, “Introduction,” in *Keywords for Modern India*, ed. Craig Jeffrey and John Harriss (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014), 3.

7 Raymond Williams, *Keywords: A Vocabulary of Culture and Society* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1983 [1976]), 14.

over time are keys that open doors of understanding and analysis of particular cultures and societies.⁸

Williams had a profound influence not only on cultural studies but on many related fields and the idea of keywords has by now entered multiple domains of knowledge. Studies using the keywords lens have appeared, for example, in the fields of gender studies, politics, youth studies and big data, to name a few.⁹ Turning to studies of the Indonesian-Malay world, several discussions of what I consider keywords come to mind, albeit without using this term, i.e., studies of the local and cultural significance of words like *amuk*, *halus* and *rasa*.¹⁰ Whereas Firth and Williams used an intuitive or hermeneutic approach in the selection of keywords, in which an individual scholar determined a list of words deemed culturally “significant” (and what is viewed as significant will vary, and change with time), in recent years we witness a shift to a statistically based approach to the study of keywords (at least for the more “frequently studied” languages), with software that has a keyword function and findings that are determined by words’ relative frequency in and across texts, independent of personal views and preferences.¹¹

I am interested in asking what the idea of keywords can contribute to the study of the third translation paradigm, that of interlinear translations from Arabic into Javanese. Such an interlinear translation, which presents an Arabic text with a word-for-word Javanese translation appearing between its lines,

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- 8 *Keywords* appeared in 202 editions published between 1976 and 2017, including translations into Arabic, Turkish, Spanish, French and Thai, for some of which see: <https://www.worldcat.org/formats-editions/953458999?author=Williams%2C+Raymond>.
- 9 The Keywords Feminist Editorial Collective, eds., *Keywords for Gender and Sexuality Studies* (New York: NYU Press, 2021); Daniel T. Rodgers, *Contested Truths: Keywords in American Politics since Independence* (New York: Basic Books, 1987); Nancy Lesko and Susan Talburt, eds., *Keywords in Youth Studies: Tracing Affects, Movements, Knowledge* (New York: Routledge, 2012); Nanna Bonde Thylstrup et al., eds., *Uncertain Archives: Critical Keywords for Big Data* (Boston: MIT Press, 2021). It is noteworthy that in two fields that are relevant to my own research, translation studies and religious studies, not much seems to have been written about keywords as compared with other fields.
- 10 Being keywords, these words cannot be easily translated or defined but a simplistic attempt would yield “running amuck” (derived from Malay *amok*), on which see Eduardo Ugarte, “Running Amok: The Demoniacal Impulse,” *Asian Studies Review* 16, no. 1 (1992): 182–189; “refined”(halus), see Clifford Geertz, *The Religion of Java* (Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1960), 232; and “taste, flavor, sensibility, mood” (*rasa*) on which see Nancy K. Florida, *Writing the Past, Inscripting the Future: History as Prophecy in Colonial Java* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 1995), 176.
- 11 For a study of travel writing based on a statistical model of assessing keywords, see Andrea Gerbig, “Key Words and Key Phrases in a Corpus of Travel Writing: From Early Modern English Literature to Contemporary “blooks,” in *Keyness in Texts*, ed. Marina Bondi and Mike Scott (Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 2010), 147–68.

is a space where vocabularies, grammars, ideas, and entire histories carried by and through language encounter one another on the page. It is also a space in which—and here this translation paradigm or method differs from others—the unit of analysis is often the single word, sometimes even the preposition or suffix. Because many of these translations take care to translate every word, and often separately and not necessarily within a sentence that can be read and understood in an idiomatic manner, it is important to seek corresponding ways to analyze the translation language that also emphasize the same level of the individual word. The idea of keywords offers one path to do so.

And so I set out thinking about Islamic keywords in Arabic which I could examine in their translation or non-translation into Javanese. My premise was that the religious sphere contains words that express and represent core values or ideas of a tradition and that interlinear translations, which lie at the edge of the translation continuum in that they are, or seem to be, very literal at the word and also the syntax level, would be a productive site in which to identify such keywords and explore what happened as they “crossed the lines,” so to speak, into another language.

The study of interlinear translations from the region is still in its early stages, and these translations are clearly varied yet little studied and documented and therefore conclusions would be premature. However, with this important caveat in mind, and from material gathered to date, it seems that the majority of extant interlinear translations were produced in pedagogical settings of Islamic learning and belong to theological, legal and ritualistic genres. In such texts, which offer instruction on a range of religious matters from faith articles to daily practice, precision is highly valued. But what transpires in other interlinear genres? The number of interlinear translations that include narrative sections I have encountered thus far is small and yet I find it especially intriguing to examine such narratives and see how translators working within the interlinear, word-for-word paradigm which appears relatively rigid, engaged with stories which by nature tend to be more fluid than the other genres mentioned above. Among such texts are those belonging to the *Maulid* genre, which is the example selected for this study.¹²

12 Throughout this article words and names that are derived from Arabic but that are used on a regular basis in Indonesian and Javanese and have become “naturalized” in those languages, like *maulid*, are spelled according to their common orthographies.

Maulid: a Brief Introduction

Maulid (or *Kitab Maulid*, or *Maulud*) is both a literary genre and a religious practice to commemorate the birth of the Prophet Muhammad.¹³ Such texts became widespread from the late twelfth century onwards in different Arab regions and subsequently moved across languages, regions and cultures.¹⁴ *Maulid* texts center on hagiographies and prayers for the Prophet. They are usually written in Arabic but sometimes in local languages, and are often composed in a combination of both poetry and prose. In addition to being recited on the Prophet's birthday they also accompany celebrations such as marriages and circumcisions.

Within the genre of *Maulid* there are a large number of well-known texts, of which the most popular in Southeast Asia is the anonymous *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* ("The Birth of the Best of Mankind").¹⁵ This popularity is attested, for example, in all twenty-two copies and partial copies of this text listed in the catalogue of Arabic manuscripts in the Netherlands originating from Indonesia.¹⁶

After the Qur'ān, the *Maulid* is the most frequently and finely illuminated genre of Islamic texts in Southeast Asia, a fact that is apparent also in the manuscript I discuss, which is illuminated throughout. According to Annabel Gallop, who has documented sixty illuminated *Kitab Maulid* from all corners of the Malay world, they evidence much more varied and individualistic artistic formats than the illuminated Qur'āns. Very few are dated but most can be presumed to be from the nineteenth century with a few from the eighteenth century.¹⁷

Among the *Kitab Maulid* from the Indonesian-Malay world there are several that include an interlinear translation from Arabic into a local language.¹⁸

13 It is celebrated on the 12th day of Rabī' al-awwal, the third month in the Hijri calendar.

14 Ines Weinrich, "From the Arab Lands to the Malabar Coast. The Arabic Mawlid as a Literary Genre and a Traveling Text," *Entangled Religions* 11, no. 5 (2022).

15 I follow the common Indonesian spelling of the Arabic title.

16 P. Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands* (Leiden: Brill, 1980).

17 Gallop, Annabel Teh, "In praise of the Prophet: illuminated Kitab Mawlid manuscripts from Southeast Asia," Contribution to 'Oceans that Speak' exhibition, Islamic Arts Museum Malaysia, scheduled for July 2024, forthcoming.

18 For a comparative study of five such manuscripts, see Ronit Ricci, "Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the Maulid Syaraf al-Anām Across the Indonesian-Malay World," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51 (2023): 143–64.

Babad Maulud

The manuscript that is the focus of my discussion is a *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* from Java, known also as *Babad Maulud* (“*babad*” indicating a genre of Javanese historiography), written in Arabic with a Javanese translation in *pegon* script written between the lines. The manuscript includes some marginal notes, all in Arabic, referring to and elaborating on various words or scenes depicted in the main text. Written on Dutch paper measuring 330 x 205 mm and containing 79 folios, it is illuminated throughout in red, green, black and gold with double frames, columns and many marginal ornaments. It is currently housed at the British Library, MS. Or 16873, dated 1864/65 (1281 Hijri).¹⁹ The translator is not named nor is a place mentioned. In addition to prayers and supplications for the Prophet, as well as poetic verses describing him, the *Babad* tells the story of the events preceding the Prophet’s birth, depicts the birth itself, and some of what followed. My focus is, as mentioned, on the narrative rather than the poetic sections.

I have presently identified four main “translation types” in the *Maulud* manuscript, reflecting in turn different strategies employed by the translator at the word level:

1. Arabic/Islamic words that remain as is in the translation (although often somewhat modified because of an altered pronunciation). Some examples include Arabic *qiyāma* (Judgement Day), *qawm* (a people), *muʿjizāt* (miracles), *kāfir* (infidel), *rusul* (messengers), *rahma* (mercy).
2. Arabic words that are “translated” by using an Arabic synonym or closely related word (which may have been more familiar or considered as Javanese): *sifah* is translated as *zina* (adultery), *al-aḥyān* as *zaman* (time/s), *yawm al-nushūr* as *qiyamat* (Judgement Day), *makhtūn* as *sinunatan* (circumcised, here with the Javanese passive form infix inserted). This category is rather limited in size.
3. Arabic words that are translated into Javanese, clearly by far the largest category, which includes all types of vocabulary and language elements. A few examples are *jall* translated as *mulia*, *nūr* (light) as *cahaya*, *jamāl* (beauty) as *bagus*, *ḥabīb* (beloved) as *kĕkasih*. In this category there are many words that capture characteristics of God and Prophet. This is also where we can identify much intercultural transmission, infusing new

19 The manuscript is listed in M.C. Ricklefs, P. Voorhoeve & A.T. Gallop, *Indonesian Manuscripts in Great Britain. New Edition with Addenda et Corrigenda*. (Jakarta: EFEO, 2014), 287. It can be viewed online at http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?index=23&ref=Or_16873.

meaning into old Sanskritic words, e.g., *al-janna*, “the garden” or paradise is rendered as *swarga*, *al-nār*, “the fire” or hell as *naraka*; *khūr al-‘ayn* (the beautiful-eyed women of paradise) as *widadari*.²⁰

4. Words of Javanese cultural importance that do not appear in the Arabic text and are additions made by the translator. This is what we can call, following Ortega and Becker, a form of “exuberance” in translation.²¹ This category forms an exception to this particular translation paradigm for which close adherence to the source is the defining dimension.

Although I initially set out to examine the kinds of words included in the first to third translation types listed above, intending to explore Islamic keywords in Arabic and their translation or non-translation into Javanese, I found myself noticing certain silences: places where the Arabic was silent about something deemed important in Javanese, or, one might say, where the Arabic had exhibited a deficiency or a shortcoming from the Javanese point of view. It is therefore the fourth category—that of added Javanese words—which I consider here. Why were words added? Was it mainly for clarification? Elaboration? Was it a form of acculturation to a Javanese world of relationships and values?

Added in Translation

The one element which was deemed very important in the Javanese translation but not in the Arabic was the use of titles and honorifics, or more broadly the practice of almost never referring to a person (whether exalted or derided), by their name alone. The pervasive use of titles/honorifics is a way to situate individuals within a social context, demarcating their relationship to others. I wish to explore these added words as keywords, in this case a cluster of interrelated words that, as Williams suggested in his own examples of word clusters, should

20 The Sanskritic words *swarga*, *naraka* and *widadari* were embedded in the Hindu-Buddhist religious and literary world of pre-Islamic Java. *Swarga* referred to the realm of the gods and *naraka* to the realm of the demons, both sites of potential rebirth within a cosmology of cyclical time, very different from the Islamic finality of either heaven or hell after death. *Widadari* referred to celestial nymphs and did not carry the association of beautiful women awaiting pious men in the afterlife.

21 Becker’s discussion refers to exuberance as meanings added to words or utterances that go beyond the original’s intent or semantic field, to a way in which every utterance conveys more than it intends. In the *Maulid*, however, the exuberance in translation is more explicit and refers to an addition of words rather than associations in the reader or listener’s mind, and yet the two forms have much in common. On “exuberance” and its counterpart “deficiency” in translation, see A.L Becker, *Beyond Translation: Essays Toward a Modern Philology* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 1995), 5–6.

be examined together to shed light on important ideas and processes within a given culture and period. Such clusters are made up of “cultural keywords” that, Levisen and Waters write, “govern the shared cognitive outlook of speakers and encode certain culture-specific logics, and impose on their speakers a certain interpretative grid through which they make sense of the world.”²²

The narrative of the Prophet’s birth as told in the *Babad Maulud* mentions various figures who played a role in the events depicted including family members, religious scholars and several of the prophets who preceded Muhammad. In the Arabic text these names appear for the most part as such, with no titles or honorifics added. Looking to the Javanese text, however, one can see that the translator took care to preface many of the names with a title. In Javanese, prophets’ names are prefixed with *nabi*, the Arabic word for “prophet,” e.g. *nabi* Muhammad, *nabi* Ibrahim, *nabi* Adam, *nabi* Isa; beyond the ubiquitous “nabi” the Prophet Muhammad’s name was often also prefaced with the royal *kangjĕng* or its abbreviated form *jĕng*; women have *siti*, *mbok*, *dewi* or a combination of these titles attached to their names, as in *siti* Amina or *mbok dewi* Amina (the Prophet’s mother), *dewi* Maryam (the sister of Moses) and *mbok* Halima (the Prophet’s nursemaid); the names of religious scholars or authoritative figures who reliably transmitted events of early Muslim history were prefixed with *shaykh*, e.g. *shaykh* Qutāba, *shaykh* Wahab and *shaykh* Zajāj; the honorific *kyai* or in its abbreviated form *ki*, typically applied to venerable men including religious teachers and to sacred heirlooms, was also used for high status men and religious authorities: *ki* Abd al-Mutalib (the Prophet’s grandfather), *ki* Abdallah, *kyai* Yazid and *kyai* Wahab; a king’s name followed the title *raja* (e.g. *raja* Pirngon, Pharaoh).²³ [See Figures 1 and 2]

Especially interesting is how on both extremes of this continuum of titles and their accompanying status—at the lowest and highest ends—the practice of entitling is strictly followed. Thus, at the bottom of the hierarchy are found the infidels (*kapir*) and the hypocrites (*munapik*), both groups derided and despised within the broader framework of early Islamic history. They are mentioned in the *Maulud* as *si kapir* and *si munapik*: they are treated as a faceless collective or as anonymous wrong doers—nameless—and yet they receive a

22 Carsten Levisen and Sophia Waters, eds., *Cultural Keywords in Discourse* (Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 2017), 3.

23 As for the latter, Fir’awn (Pharaoh) is in fact also a title but has come to be employed as the name of ancient Egypt’s ruler during the events surrounding the Israelites’ struggle to escape their enslavement, the ten plagues, etc., as recounted in the book of Exodus, in the Qur’an and in the *Isrā’iliyyāt* traditions.

FIGURE 1 The following titles (in bold) are added: **Kyai Yazid, Kyai Abdallah, Kyai Wahab, Siti Amina, Jeng Rasulallah.** British Library Ms. Or 16873 f. 19v

Note: The final example, Jeng Rasulallah, exhibits a Javanese title (*jeng*) added to another title, or epithet, *rasulullah* (God's Messenger) which appears in the Arabic to refer to the Prophet.

FIGURE 2 The following titles (in bold) are added: **Raja Pirngon, Dewi Maryam.** British Library Ms. Or 16873 f. 24v

title.²⁴ On the opposite end, at the pinnacle of the hierarchy expressed via titles is Allah, for whom the royal title *gusti* (lord, master) is employed. According to Koentjaraningrat's study of Javanese terms for God and supernatural beings a distinction between pre-Islamic deities and Islamic supernatural beings is

24 The dictionary defines *si* as follows: 1. deprecatory person marker, used before the names of those with whom the speaker and interlocutor are intimate, e.g., *simbok* (our) mother, *simbah* (our) grandmother. 2. A particle used before a noun referring to a particular person in a category. Stuart Robson and Singgih Wibisono, *Javanese-English Dictionary* (Jakarta: Periplus, 2002), 677.

maintained in Java through a difference in terms of address used for the two categories, with Allah, the prophets and the walis associated with power, high office and high rank through the use of titles for kings and high officials, like *gusti*, *kangjèng* and *sunan*.²⁵

Javanese is a hierarchic language with a range of speech styles that are determined by different parameters of the speaker and the one he or she is speaking to or about. Such parameters include age and gender but also the social status—perceived, real or claimed—of those involved. How exactly Javanese developed historically to reach this state is a matter that has been debated by scholars, linguists in particular, but is still far from being fully understood.²⁶ Capturing the speech of the distant past is of course impossible unless recorded in writing and few studies have examined the way speech styles were expressed in literature.²⁷ Although it is beyond the scope of this article, considering the pervasive use of titles in the *Maulid's* translation is certainly encompassed within the broader sphere of speech style usage in Javanese, expressed through differentiated verbs, pronouns and adjectives selected for use based on the status of individuals communicating with one another or being described. These subtleties are another realm in which the translation is exuberant, adding nuance that is not present in the Arabic: in this case it is not words that are added, as with the titles, but rather the addition takes the form of expressive diversification through the use of speech styles that are prevalent in Javanese but not in Arabic.²⁸

25 Koentjaraningrat, "Javanese Terms for Gods and Supernatural Beings," in *Man, Meaning and History. Essays in Honor of H.G. Schulte Nordholt*, ed. R. Schefold, J.W. Schoorl and J. Tennekes (Leiden: Brill, 1980), 132–33.

26 Examples include E.M. Uhlenbeck, *A Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Java and Madura* (The Hague: Martinus Nijhoff, 1964); J. Joseph Errington, *Structure and Style in Javanese. A Semiotic View of Linguistic Etiquette* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1988); J. Joseph Errington, *Language and Social Change in Java: Linguistic Reflexes of Modernization in a Traditional Royal Polity* (Athens: Ohio University Press, 1985). For a brief introduction on the Javanese language, its speech styles (referred to as levels) and honorifics, see John U. Wolff and Soepomo Poedjosoedarmo, *Communicative Codes in Central Java* (Ithaca: Cornell SEAP Publications, 2002 [1982]), 1–9.

27 For one such rare study, in which speech styles are analyzed based on Javanese novels written between 1913–1941, see Subandi Djajengwasito, "Javanese Speech Styles: A Multiple Discriminant Analysis of Social Constraints" (PhD diss., Cornell University, 1975). For a brief history of the study of Javanese speech styles, see 12–15.

28 This too is beyond the scope of my discussion but is important to note as within the larger study of interlinear translation I am looking at different, often subtle changes between original and translation. This change—the use of Javanese speech styles to translate an Arabic that does not employ them—is major, but can remain invisible if a quantitative

Names and Titles in Java

In Java naming has been a complex phenomenon. Describing it in 1869, almost precisely at the time the *Babad Maulud* was inscribed, the Dutch missionary and scholar Poensen pointed to the numerous occasions that brought about a bestowing of a name or a new name throughout a person's life in Java, from birth through marriage, parenthood, moments of experiencing both good and ill fortune, and more.²⁹ And a person's name should always be prefaced with a title of some sort, one that situates him or her within a web of social relations. The importance of the use of such titles in Javanese is highlighted by the existence of a special verb, *njangkar*, to refer to someone by name only, omitting his or her title, which can be done under terms of intimacy or contempt or when speaking to a person occupying a subordinate position. When addressing or referring to superiors or those with whom one is not intimate the use of titles is obligatory.³⁰

In addition to Poensen, the Dutch orientalist and colonial administrator L.W.C. van den Berg was also writing about Javanese titles at more or less the time of the *Babad Maulud's* inscription. Whereas Poensen penned an article, van den Berg dedicated an entire book to a discussion of "the native ranks and titles of Java and Madura." In his preface he noted that the subject of titles in Javanese society had long been of interest to Europeans and that a detailed, comprehensive study was in order after several decades of surveys that did not quite deliver the desired results. The work covers different areas on the two islands thus offering information about regional variation as well as what Van den Berg saw as the main categories of ranks and titles (which possessed some overlap amongst them), i.e., noble, official, and royal titles, and those he termed titles of honor and courtesy. Clearly the subject was of importance to the colonial government at a time when it was increasingly intervening in the Javanese political system and to some extent altering it, but what also comes through these contemporary writings is how complex, pervasive and puzzling

method of counting the words in both languages or comparing original and translation in a technical matter is followed.

- 29 Carel Poensen, "Iets over Javaansche naamgeving en eigennamen [On Javanese Name-giving and Proper Names]", *Mededeelingen van wege het Nederlandsche Zendelinggenootschap* XIV (1870): 304–21. Poensen contrasted these customs with those known to him from Europe where, he suggested, naming seemed much more straightforward.
- 30 See Koentjaraningrat, "Javanese Terms," 132.

to the Dutch was this system and how significant it was for them to grasp, map and control it as so central a dimension of Javanese society.³¹

Not only Dutch scholarship of the period engaged with the matter. The *Sĕrat Babad Ila-Ila*, a history of Javanese traditions compiled in 1913 but drawing heavily on Ronggowarsito's mid-nineteenth century *Pustaka Raja Purwa*, includes notes on Javanese rituals, customs and performing arts, and contains a Javanese history of naming and titles.³² It dedicates a chapter to the history of naming in Java long ago, beginning with the instatement of time reckoning according to the *sangkala* (chronogram) years.³³ During the early days every person carried the same name from birth and throughout life, a custom that changed gradually, as did the use and addition of many titles put forth in the text. Citing the *Kitab Waliwana*³⁴ the *Ila-Ila* states that since 1414 the Javanese have been followers of Islam and with this shift titles were changed to accord with the new religion, e.g., *maharsi* (from Sanskrit: "great seer") became *susu-hunan* (a title for a king in Java), and *biku* (from Sanskrit: ascetic, mendicant) *kyai agĕng*.³⁵ The depiction of this process proves a point made in scholarship, both older and more recent, on Javanese name-giving practices: that changes in their patterns reveal important societal shifts. For example, as Askuri and Kuipers show, an analysis of Arabic names over a century in Java can be studied as a yardstick of Islamization.³⁶ Thus insights from studies of naming, which have been more numerous and detailed than those about titles, should be considered in tandem as both forms of address—names and titles—reflect changing personal and collective affiliations.

31 Since Poensen and Van den Berg's time, scholars of Java have continued to study the topics of naming and employing titles and to comment on their centrality to understanding social relations and status, located as they are at the crossroads of linguistics, history, anthropology, and cultural studies. Here, however, I focus mainly on the period of the manuscript's production.

32 The Indonesian translation and transliteration does not mention the manuscript it is based on but it is most likely MS. MN 255, see Nancy K. Florida, *Javanese Literature in Surakarta Manuscripts: Manuscripts of the Mangkunagaran Palace* (Ithaca: Cornell SEAP, 2000), 164.

33 *Sĕrat Babad Ila Ila*, translit. and trans. into Indonesian Moelyono Sastronaryatmo (Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 1986), 222–29.

34 This may well be a typo for the well-known *Kitab Walisana* (or *Sĕrat Walisana*).

35 *Ibid.*, 226. Almost all titles mentioned are non-Muslim and closely tied to Javanese nobility and pre-Islamic religious roles.

36 Askuri Askuri and Joel C. Kuipers, "The Politics of Arabic Naming and Islamization in Java. Processes of Hybridization and Purification," *al-Jāmi'ah: Journal of Islamic Studies* 56, no. 1 (2018): 59–94.

The *Babad Maulud*: Further Thoughts on Titles

The titles in the *Babad Maulud* could be divided into several categories, which themselves are fluid and often overlapping. Some of the titles employed, although deeply embedded in the Javanese “system,” are in Arabic (shaykh, *nabi*) or derived from the sphere of religious Arabic (*siti*, possibly from *sayyidatī*, the feminine form of *sayyid*: master, leader, one who is a descendant of the Prophet Muhammad). Some titles are associated with Javanese royalty and the highest nobility (*kangjěng*, *gusti*); *dewi* is often associated with pre-Islamic goddesses, queens or princesses (e.g., the rice goddess Dewi Sri, the Ramayana heroine Dewi Sinta); titles can also be based in kinship terms, i.e., *mbok* (mother). These divisions can be arranged differently and, rather than reflecting Islamic and other terminologies, could be based on royal authority, including raja, *gusti* and *kangjěng*; religious eminence, e.g., *nabi*, *kyai* and shaykh; and on familial/genealogical ties, i.e., *siti* and *mbok*, or on gender: *nabi*, shaykh, *ki* and raja for males; *siti*, *dewi* and *mbok* for females; *gusti*, *kangjěng*, *si* for either.

The addition of titles in the translation raises the question of the relationship between the use of titles and terms of address in spoken language and in the world of written texts. Again turning to Poensen’s contemporary observations, he comments, after discussing naming practices at length and in detail, that there is another custom among the Javanese “which often marginalizes the use of the name.”³⁷ This was the custom of using titles to refer to individuals, of which Poensen offers several examples: *Gus* (from *bagus*, a polite term of address by adults to boys or youth), *Kang* (from *kakang*, older brother, a term of address used also for one’s husband), *Yu* (from *ayu*, pretty; Robson believes it derives from *bakyu*, older sister), *Dhi* (from *adhi*, Younger sibling, wife), *Le* (from *tole*, affectionate term for little boy, lad), *Ger* (from *anggèr*, term of address for male or female youths), all used to address one another and chosen based on the interrelationships of age, rank, and kinship amongst speakers.³⁸ In other words, with all due respect to naming and renaming throughout one’s life, the use of titles or address terms was very prevalent and often overshadowed names in daily interactions.³⁹ In a much later study de Grave viewed names and titles not as two distinct categories but as overlapping ones, as when children address a younger first cousin as *dhik* (younger

37 Poensen, “Iets over Javaansche naamgeving,” 316.

38 Poensen, “Iets over Javaansche naamgeving,” 316.

39 Jean-Marc de Grave, “Naming as a Dynamic Process: The Case of Javanese Personal Names,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 39, no. 113 (2011): 71, 74.

sibling), or a wife addresses her husband with *kakang* (older brother), terms that can be used on their own or be followed by a name. These studies point to titles as important markers of identity in Javanese society, at times even more important than, or at least as important as individual names, a tendency that helps explain why adding titles to names in the *Babad Maulud* was so important for localizing the text in Java.

Further overlap can be discerned between some titles and pronouns. Pronouns, which are a pivotal element of the Javanese speech styles, are also more nuanced in the translation than in the Arabic text, but this is another theme that cannot be addressed in detail here. The main example in the *Babad* concerns *tuwan* which in literary Javanese and Malay at the time the text was inscribed meant “lord” or “lady” but in spoken language was employed to respectfully address male government officials, commercial superiors and all Europeans, regardless of their social position, in Java’s big cities in the nineteenth century.⁴⁰ During that period *tuwan* also formed an element of names given to children (both male and female) born in colonial Ceylon to families that traced their ancestry to the Indonesian archipelago, including to Java, and therefore had a triple function there as name, title and pronoun. In the *Babad* the title *tuwan* is used as a polite masculine second person singular personal pronoun (“you”) translating Arabic *anta*, and as a polite masculine second person singular possessive pronoun (“your”) translating the Arabic suffix *-ka* (e.g., *aṣḥābika*, “your friends” translated as *rowang tuwan*).

The structure of the text on the pages of *Babad Maulud* may hint at the process of inserting titles into the Javanese translation of the Arabic text: the Arabic is written in dark black ink, each line framed with black and gold, with space left beneath the Arabic and within the frame to fill in the translation. This format is especially evident in the pages toward the text’s conclusion where no translation was added and so the sequence of writing—first laying out the full Arabic text, then adding the translation—is clear (see Figure 3). One can easily imagine the translator going about his work and, whenever reaching a protagonist’s name, feeling compelled to add a title based on conventional language use at the time. And not only the translator as he read and composed the translation but also other readers coming after him would have felt the lack had titles not been added. The Arabic *maulid* text was recited at gatherings on various occasions with the audience joining in for refrains and the poetry sections with some knowing the entire text by heart.⁴¹ One such occasion is

40 Elizabeth P. Wittermans, “Indonesian Terms of Address in a Situation of Rapid Change,” *Social Forces* 46, no. 1 (1967): 49.

41 See Nico Kaptein, “The Berdiri Mawlid issue among Indonesian Muslims in the period from circa 1875 to 1930,” *BKI* 49, no. 1 (1993): 125–26. For the case of *maulid* recitations

FIGURE 3 Arabic text with vacant “translation spaces.” British Library MS. Or 16873 f. 69v

depicted briefly in the *Babad Jaka Tingkir*, where the *maulid*'s poetic sections (*singir*) and its various reciters singing at the Demak Mosque on the eve of Garebegan Mulud are mentioned but not the language of the text, which was most likely Arabic.⁴² We cannot be certain about public readings of the Javanese interlinear translation but perhaps, like many other Javanese texts at the time, this one too was recited aloud. If that was the case there could have been listeners who would have found it unacceptable to recite all those names of pious and admired figures without according them the proper titles. If this explanation is plausible the interlinear translation may hint at the interface between the spoken and the written—if avoiding titles was unthinkable in speech and daily life, especially when considering those respected and possessing high status, then translating the Arabic without adding those titles would have seemed irreverent.

It is also worth considering the particular choice of titles employed in the *Maulid*'s translation into Javanese. The titles “make sense” in that they are highly conventional and oft-used in Javanese Islamic literature of the period. Perhaps the most notable example in this regard is the recurring appearance of

in Malabar, see Muneer A. Kuzhiyan, “Poetics of Piety: Genre, Self-fashioning and the Mappila Lifescape,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 26, no. 3 (2016): 423–41.

42 For the Javanese text, see M. Sastronaryatmo, translit. and trans., *Babad Jaka Tingkir Babad Pajang* (Jakarta: Proyek Penerbitan Buku Sastra dan Daerah, 1981), 269. For a translation and analysis, see Florida, *Writing the Past*, 183–84 and 358, respectively.

No doubt similar depictions, possibly with more explicit detail on *maulid* texts' linguistic dimensions, are scattered across Javanese Islamic manuscripts and deserve further investigation.

“*nabi* Muhammad” or “*kangjǐng nabi*” in the translation whenever the Prophet Muhammad is mentioned.⁴³ However, especially in light of some of the detailed, contemporary studies of Javanese practices of naming and bestowing titles and ranks cited above, one must not lose sight of the fact that a very broad range of titles (royal, official, familial etc.) were common in Javanese society at the time of the manuscript’s inscription and although some (those of colonial officials, for example) can be deemed inappropriate for insertion into a narrative depicting events in seventh-century Arabia, one could also argue that some of those titles that *were* employed were also “out of place” within a depiction of the Prophet’s time and so that “appropriateness” or lack thereof is in itself not a helpful characteristic with which to define title choice. Thus Wittermans, in her study on change in Indonesian terms of address as reflecting social and political processes, discussed the developing overlap of local feudal and colonial systems in nineteenth-century Java, where “behavioral patterns that characterized reciprocal relations between aristocrats and commoners were extended to those between plantation manager and worker, between colonial administrator and those living in the territory under his control.” Within this context she notes that in prewar east and central Java, where Javanese was spoken, European administrators and plantation managers were addressed as *kangjǐng*, a term which earlier had been reserved only for the highest Javanese aristocracy and within Javanese-Islamic texts, for the Prophet. Thus the inclusion of Europeans within the Javanese hierarchical system was expressed through their titles, showing that title-selection was a dynamic process and that it could reflect both traditional norms and changing circumstances.⁴⁴

Further, comparative study is required to address the issue of title choice in more detail but for now the point to be made is that decisions taken about inclusion or exclusion of particular titles draw our attention to what enters a translation at a given historical moment and what does not, inviting us to look more closely at the confluence of a prior, highly popular Arabic devotional text, its word for word translation into Javanese, and the social and political realities at the time of writing which may have shaped the translator’s choices.

43 It is important to note that although the Prophet conventionally received a title shared with members of the Javanese royalty and high nobility, i.e., *kangjǐng*, in his case it was always appended to the more weighty and religiously charged *nabi*. So whereas *kangjǐng* was used for both royalty and the Prophet, I am unaware of an example of the use of *nabi* for a Javanese figure.

44 Wittermans, “Indonesian Terms,” 48.

Concluding Reflections

Interlinear texts and their analysis can point us—perhaps where the translation is not precise more than where it is—to keywords, concepts, and social values or practices in a given place and time. Applying a range of titles to a narrative situated in seventh-century Arabia within a word for word translation that for the most part attempts to duplicate the original—and in that original titles are seldom used and names appear without them—points to a key cultural feature that was retained in Javanese despite the more general translation strategy. Titles, bestowed on everyone from exalted God to the lowliest *kafir*, form a very clear exception of word addition within the interlinear translation of the text. Their insertion points to a practice that tied in with broader questions of social etiquette, hierarchy, identity and genealogy.⁴⁵

We find here a translation element which is not strictly about linguistic shift as some of the titles added in translation, like *nabi* or *shaykh*, were in Arabic, the language of the original *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* that was being translated into Javanese. Such examples blur the lines between the two texts and two languages written on the page. The theme of titles is one that shows some of the nuance within the interlinear translation paradigm: so far I have discussed the addition of titles as an exuberance of the Javanese translation, and yet Arabic, which appears to remain silent in many of the instances where Javanese “speaks” to situating one in society, also presents a system of titles which is partially adapted into Javanese. Whereas the Javanese titles explored in this study for the most part denote social status, those of the Arabic text emphasize ancestry. When examples of this phenomenon appear, the Javanese translation follows the Arabic use of patronyms, i.e., so and so was the son of so and so, sometimes across several generations, thus adopting the model of situating

45 Although I have focused mainly on contemporary sources from around the time of the manuscript’s inscription for context there is relevance also in later studies that explore the role and importance of titles and terms of address in Javanese, especially in the realm of religion. Robson’s study of the use of titles in prayer shows that in the 1990s Javanese Christians in the area of Muntilan, Central Java, preferred to pray in Javanese rather than in Indonesian in part because omitting titles in the latter was perceived as improper whereas their use in Javanese meant that Javanese had the resources needed to express the proper relationship between man and God. For example, in the Hail Mary the Javanese employed Dewi Maria and Sri Yesus whereas Indonesian had simply “Maria” and “Yesus,” title-less. The assertion that “titles are an indication and an acknowledgment of the status accorded to a respected person, and hence not to be omitted” rings true for the late twentieth-century Christian prayer as it does for the mid-nineteenth century Islamic translation. Stuart Robson. “Speaking to God in Javanese.” *L’Homme* 34, no. 132 (1994): 133–42. https://www.persee.fr/doc/hom_0439-4216_1994_num_34_132_369832.

individuals within their familial lineage, but apparently that was deemed insufficient, and titles were added.

For example:

Yazīd ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn Wahb
*Kyai Yazid anak lanange kyai Abdallah anak lanange kyai Wahab*⁴⁶

In some cases, the Javanese explains a familial connection differently from the Arabic:

‘Abdallāh ibn ‘Abd al-Muṭṭalib ibn Hāshim
*Ki Abdallah kang putëra ki Abd al-Mutalib kang putëra wayah Hashim*⁴⁷

According to the Arabic ‘Abdallāh was the son of ‘Abd al-Muṭṭalib, son of Hāshim, but the Javanese describes him as *ki Abdallah*, son of *Abd al-Mutalib*, grandson of Hashim.

Here the Javanese employs both a patronym (son of ‘Abd al-Muṭṭalib) and an avonym (grandson of Hāshim) while the Arabic consistently emphasizes the bond between father and son. It would be interesting to consider what brought about this shift. The point, however, is to stress that the translation did include the instances where Arabic genealogical lineages were noted but also added markers of social rank. Status did not replace ancestry, rather, it was added to it.

Interlinear translations overflow with detail. Single words, even prefixes, can become units of analysis or entry points to the complexities of these texts. There are of course risks in relying on single words as “anchors” or “pillars” of an entire culture, a period or a religious tradition. The example discussed in this article, that of adding titles to names in the Javanese translation, can seem minor and could have easily been overlooked or dismissed. But beginning with something small, almost imperceptible, in order to offer a glimpse of a broader cultural or linguistic phenomenon is one thing philology does best. We might think of keywords as the younger sibling or descendants of older studies in etymology and philology. And Williams’ long list of keywords and his emphasis on word clusters created less reliance on this or that word as being somehow representative in its own right, even if his, too, was clearly only a

46 The Arabic reads: Yazīd son of ‘Abdallāh son of Wahb. The Javanese reads: Kyai Yazid male child of kyai Abdallah male child of kyai Wahab. The Arabic *ibn* is masculine but the Javanese *anak* is not gendered and so here, and in many other instances, the translation adds words to clarify that aspect, another exuberance.

47 Here rather than use *anak* (child) the gendered word *putëra* (son) is employed, rendering gender markers redundant.

partial attempt to pin down the elusive workings of language and humanity. I see the added titles as a form of what Williams called an interrelated cluster, words that are connected, entangled with one another, here within the history of members of Javanese society addressing one another, and others from without. Looking closely at the use of titles in the *Babad Maulud* is one way to think about social relations, religious authority and identity in the world of Javanese Islam, its texts and lived experience, at a particular moment in time. It is a way to consider cultural keywords, in this case titles, as “culturally laden words around which whole discourses are organized,”⁴⁸ which rings especially true if we consider examples like *nabi*, *kyai*, *gusti* and *mbok*.

The study of keywords, inspired by Williams but adapted by scholars to different and shifting cultural and theoretical contexts, offers a point of entry into analyzing interlinear translation, a practice central to the development of Islam in Java over several centuries. And while the study of interlinear translation is certainly important to better understanding the “Arabization” of Javanese, it also has the potential to highlight the “Javanization” of the Arabic text as received in Javanese society. No less importantly, it allows an awareness of, and a certain level of access to, cultural encounters unfolding at particular moments, negotiated through a translation strategy that prioritized close, word-level adherence to an original, yet also created its spaces of exception.

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48 Levisen and Waters, *Cultural Keywords*, 3.

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